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Big Data Analytics for Education: Hadoop and Spark

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ABSTRACT

In the last decade, the amount of data generated has increased immensely because of IoT – Internet of Things, Social networks, and Cloud. Because of this increase in the amount of data generated, each time appears new platforms for processing data. Big Data platforms tools are increasingly used in enterprises but unfortunately are not widely taught or even applied in the academic context. Hence, young engineers that have not yet become acquainted with this subject see a harder integration on the job site. Therefore, to encourage the teaching of such subject and by having in mind the sustainability on engineering education we have done a survey on Open Source Big Data platforms. In this context, we investigated two open source Big Data solutions: Apache Hadoop and Apache Spark.

Conference Key Areas: Engineering Skills; Continuing Engineering Education and Lifelong Learning; Curriculum Development.

Keywords: Big Data platforms; Hadoop; Spark.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Every day, more companies look for the possibilities and opportunities that the data offer them. There are many platforms that allow capture and analyze data, such as Hadoop, but the problem comes when the platforms take a long time to process the data. For this, new and more powerful platforms are proposed, of which one in particular stands out Apache Spark. Spark allows managing large sets of data in "short time". This improvement in performance is possible by incorporating two new technologies to process data more quickly. These two technologies are the Resilient Distributed Datasets that allow the processing of data in memory and Directed Acyclic Graph divider for creating jobs in one, two or more stages. Apache Spark increasingly is being used more because it offers many advantages with respect to other platforms.

Apache Hadoop and Apache Spark have some differences that we will analyze. One of these differences is that Hadoop uses MapReduce model and Spark does not work with this model. The principal problem of MapReduce model are transactions that are very slow. For this reason, the idea of loading the data into memory appears, since memory access is much faster than disk access. In this way Apache Spark with two new technologies RDD and DAG appears. These two technologies permit Spark to get 100x faster in memory than Hadoop, or 10x faster on disk. The principal difference is that Hadoop stores all steps – Map and Reduce – in a hard disk, while Spark stores them in a memory RAM.

Nowadays, technology is used in almost all the areas of our day to day, such as the areas of education, scientific, or health. Most of these areas incorporate different technologies, which facilitate people work. Therefore, they become essential and it is necessary people with competences in its use.

In the area of education technologies are fully put in place and have become indispensable. Increasingly schools try to adapt education to the world of technology, incorporating computers, interactive platforms and virtual laboratories. These tools allow students to view content of a particular subject over the Internet, and make and submit certain practices.

In recent years with the increase in the use of technologies, more data are generated every day by people, and conventional databases had to move to accommodate larger amount of data. Different companies have developed platforms that allow to work with massive data sets, such as Hadoop or Spark open source platforms, that would allow individuals and students to analyse and extract information from the data.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the ecosystem and architecture of Big Data Platforms, Hadoop and Spark. Section 3 describes the differences between Hadoop and Spark. Section 4 describes the related work. Finally, section 5 presents our conclusions and future work.

2 BIG DATA PLATFORMS

2.1 Apache HADOOP

Hadoop is an open source software enabling distributed processing of large data sets across groups of computers using a simple programming model. It was created in 2004 by Doug Cutting; it has its origins in Apache Nutch, an open source web search engine [1]. It was designed to scale up to hundreds and even thousands of nodes and is also highly fault tolerant [2]. In the year 2008, it became a top-level Apache

project because it was used by many major companies, such as Yahoo, Facebook and New York Times [3]. The largest contributor to the project is Yahoo!, which uses Hadoop in its business.

Hadoop is an Open Source Platform and is available for download at the following we address: <https://hadoop.apache.org/>.

The official website of Hadoop gives us a useful installation guide. On this web site, we can read how we can install Apache Hadoop, who uses Hadoop, and the news about the platform.

2.1.1 Apache Hadoop Ecosystem

Apache Hadoop has a strong ecosystem that provides many new possibilities. All projects that make up the Apache Hadoop ecosystem belong to Apache Software Foundation (ASF) [4]. In Figure 1, we can see all the projects that are part of the Apache Hadoop ecosystem.

Fig. 1. Apache Hadoop Ecosystem from [4]

The ecosystem is divided into three groups of sub-projects. Management is responsible for the management of the platform. Processing is responsible for processing the application data. Storage is responsible for storing data within the platform. Several companies such as Cloudera [5] and MapR [7] offer distributions of Hadoop which bundle a number of these projects.

2.2 Apache SPARK

Apache Spark is a fast open source cluster computing framework for Big Data processing. It is based on Hadoop's MapReduce and it extends the MapReduce model to efficiently use it for more types of computations, which includes interactive queries and stream processing [3]. Apache Spark improves the performance up to 10 times faster than on-disk data processing and offers over 80 high-level applications that can interact with different programming languages such as Java, Scala, R and Python. The main feature of Spark is its in-memory cluster computing that increases the processing speed of an application. It is designed to cover a wide range of workloads such as batch applications, iterative algorithms, interactive queries and streaming. Apache Spark was developed in 2009 at the University of California, Berkeley AMLab. In 2013, it was donated to the Apache Software Foundation. It has over 200 contributors in 50+ organizations.

Apache Spark can be implemented in 3 ways: standalone deployment, using YARN, and Spark in MapReduce [8]. All of them use the HDFS data storage system as shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Different ways to implement Apache Spark from [8]

- Standalone Deployment: Spark Standalone deployment means Spark occupies the place on top of HDFS. This way is the easiest to deploy and the one deployed with the built-in Spark EC2 scripts. Here, Spark and MapReduce will run side by side to cover all Spark jobs on a cluster.
- Hadoop Yarn Deployment: YARN is the Hadoop 2 resource manager, so it is a natural choice for those with existing Hadoop installations. It is the best solution for the enterprises that have tons of data on HDFS because they might have Hadoop users and groups and other things set up already. Spark leverages the YARN resource manager to allocate jobs on Hadoop nodes, and can run Spark applications themselves on a cluster in the cluster mode.
- Spark in MapReduce (SIMR): Spark in MapReduce is used to launch Spark job in addition to the standalone deployment. With SIMR, the user can start Spark and uses its shell without any administrative access.

Spark is an Open Source Platform and is available for download at the following we address: <http://spark.apache.org/downloads.html>.

Apache Spark has a good ecosystem because it has many important contributors. The Spark ecosystem is divided into three parts: Libraries, Spark Core and Cluster Managers. In Figure 3, we can see each of the parts that compose the ecosystem of Apache Spark [13].

Fig. 3. Apache Spark ecosystem from [13]

Spark is easy to understand when compared to its predecessor, MapReduce, which revolutionized the way to work with large data sets offering a relatively simple model for writing programs that could be run in parallel on hundreds and thousands of machines simultaneously. Thanks to its architecture, MapReduce achieves almost a linear relationship of scalability as data grows if you can add more machines and take the same. Spark maintains linear scalability and fault tolerance of MapReduce, but extends its benefits thanks to several features [8].

Apache Spark has different APIs that facilitate tasks programmers. Now let us analyze each of them:

- Spark SQL is a library that provides Apache Spark the capacity to work with structured data. This library permits querying data in the SQL format and supports many sources of data, including Hive tables, Parquet and JSON. It

allows developers to intermix SQL queries with RDDs in different programming languages, such as Python, Scala and Java. It was added to Spark in Version 1.0 [13].

- Spark Streaming is a component that allows data processing in real-time. It provides an API for manipulating data streams very similar to Spark Core's RDD API, making easier to the developers that work with real-time data. Spark Streaming was designed to provide the same degree of fault tolerance, throughput, and scalability as Spark Core [13].
- Machine Learning Library (MLlib) is a component of Apache Spark that provides multiple types of machine learning algorithms, such as classification, regression, clustering, and collaborative filtering. It also provides some lower-level Machine Learning primitives, including a generic gradient descent optimization algorithm. All of these methods are designed to scale out across a cluster [13].
- GraphX is an Apache Spark library for manipulating graphs and performing graph-parallel computations. GraphX, like Spark Streaming and Spark SQL, extends the Spark RDD API, allowing us to create directed multi-graph having properties attached to each edge and vertex. GraphX also provides various operators for manipulating graphs and a library of common graph algorithms [13].

3 BIG DATA PLATFORMS COMPARISON

In this section, we compare the two Big Data Platforms previously studied - Apache Hadoop and Apache Spark.

As it is known, Apache Hadoop and Apache Spark have some differences that we will analyze. One of these differences is that Hadoop uses the MapReduce model while Spark does not. The key problem of the MapReduce model is that transactions may be very slow. For this reason, the idea of loading the data into memory appears since memory access is much faster than disk access. In this way Apache Spark with two new technologies RDD and DAG appears. These two technologies permit Spark to get 100x faster in memory than Hadoop, or 10x faster on disk [12]. In Figure 7, we can see the differences between the intermediate calculations in Apache Spark and Apache Hadoop. The principal difference is that Hadoop stores all steps – Map and Reduce – in a hard disk, while Spark stores them in a memory RAM.

To clarify what the main differences between Spark and Hadoop are, we analyze the main terms: processing model, data processing, software requirements, programming languages and machine learning tools. First, we pay attention to processing model – this parameter gives us an important idea of the data that can be processed with each platform. In Figure 4, we can see the differences between the Hadoop and Spark processing model. Then we analyze data processing which is the way in which data are processed. There are two ways for data to be processed: in memory or on disk. Subsequently, we analyze the software requirements that are needed for the installation of either of the two platforms. Another very important point is programming languages which are the different languages that are accepted by the platform. Finally, we describe the machine learning tools consisting of different learning libraries accepted for each platform. Table 1 lists the details of these characteristics for each platform.

Fig. 4. Comparison of processing models between MapReduce and Apache Spark from [3]

Analyzing all the characteristics in Table 1, we can extract the following conclusions. When it comes to processing model, Spark is the best choice because it provides processing in both the batch and streaming model. On software requirements all frameworks require Java Development Kit (JDK), but Hadoop requires Secure Shell (SSH), too. When it comes to programming languages, the best choice is Spark because it supports a higher number of languages than Hadoop. All platforms support Java. With the Machine Learning tools, the best choice is Apache Spark because it supports MLlib, Mahout and H2O. Hadoop only supports Mahout.

On this platform, we can use Apache Spark or Apache Hadoop.

Table 1. – Hadoop MapReduce and Spark comparison

	Hadoop	Spark
Processing Model	Batch	Batch, Streaming
Data Processing	On disk (HDFS)	On disk (HDFS) or in memory
Software Requirements	JDK 1.7, SSH	JDK 1.6
Programing Languages	Java	Java, Python, R, Scala
Machine Learning Tools	Mahout	MLIB, Mahout, H2O

4 RELATED WORK

Big Data is a widely used term that has multiple definitions. In [20], a definition of Big Data based on 6V's is presented that includes the following characteristics: Volume, Velocity, Variety, Value, Variability and Veracity. In addition, [21] provides the Big Data Road Map with these phases: Data Generation, Data Acquisition, Data Storage

and Data Analysis. The number of Big Data Platforms is increasing exponentially over the next years. This creates a high number of available solutions which not only bring difficulty the choice for people wanting to select a platform for their enterprise but also create a high level of redundancy in solutions presented. Educating not only business managers but also engineering students to the potential of Big Data is crucial to guarantee the future of research and platform deployment.

In [15, 16, 20] the different technologies that can exploit the data are exposed: Parallel Computing, Distributed File System, Apache Hadoop and Data Intensive Computing. [21] also talks about the problems involved in all these new amounts of data, and provides feasible alternatives to the use of this new technology.

Currently, there are many Big Data platforms in the market and they increase daily. In [10], the authors make a comparison between the two Big Data platforms: Apache Hadoop and Apache Spark. They include a lot of interesting experiments, explaining the differences between Apache Spark's and Apache Hadoop's runtime. They executed different algorithms to obtain the results, such as Word Count, Sort, K-Means and Page Rank. In addition, they analyzed the impact in a RAM memory when these algorithms were running. In [1], the Apache Hadoop components and MapReduce model are described, and Apache Spark is presented as the future of Big Data. This paper contains only a brief description of Apache Hadoop and Spark, it does not analyze the architecture of both platforms. [8] presents the main differences between Apache Hadoop and Apache Spark, analyzing in detail the Apache Hadoop and Apache Spark platforms, explaining their architectures and how they work. In [22], the authors describe how the MapReduce model works on Hadoop and how we can create and run small Java programs with the MapReduce model. [13] provides the knowledge necessary to start working with Apache Spark. In addition, the authors explain in detail all the libraries that we can use with Spark. To know more about the Apache Spark architecture, [23] explains how RDDs (Resilient Distributed Dataset) works, its main features and how it implements in Apache Spark. Moreover, [3] provides a good comparison between Apache Spark and Apache Hadoop. In this paper, the authors analyze many differences between the two platforms, such as the execution model, supported languages, associated machine learning tools, in-memory processing, low latency, fault tolerance and enterprise support.

5 CONCLUSIONS

With the large amount of data generated today, enterprises need Big Data Platforms to process large datasets. Nowadays, the number of platforms dealing with large volumes of data, both open source and proprietary nature, is increasing, but not all the platforms can obtain a good performance in terms of runtime and accuracy for data mining. For this reason, the developers started thinking about the idea of working with data loaded in memory instead of on disk. Because of this, coming on the scene is Apache Spark that gets very good performance with large datasets. In addition, Apache Spark is open source and ready for enterprise deployment.

In this paper, we studied and compared the architecture, ecosystem and main features of Apache Spark and Apache Hadoop. Our conclusion is that Apache Spark is faster than Apache Hadoop in all the dataset sizes. In addition, Apache Spark is more accurate than Apache Hadoop. As future work, we plan to analyze these platforms to observe how they work in academic environment and identify the advantages over others Big Data platforms.

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